

PRESS SECRETARY AND INFORMATION POLICY

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Annotation: A society is a sociocommunicative system within which people, social strata, communities, etc. interact with each other. By social structure we mean the totality of classes, strata, social groups, etc. At the same time, social communities are relatively stable aggregates of people with more or less similar conditions and lifestyle, more or less similar interests (regional communities, etc.).

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A complex system of information and communication relations is one of the objects of research of a new science - social informology — the science of the laws of functioning of social information (information that reflects the life of society) and communication. At the same time, the modern press service is included in the object of social informationology, therefore, the methods of the new science are applicable for its research.

The press service has an information potential, which we consider as a set of attributive and functional properties of information transmitted by the press service to society, more precisely to the public consciousness (consciousness of the population), and as a set of means, methods and conditions that allow effective use of available information resources. To understand the attributive approach, the press service staff must know biosocial laws well, be able to apply cognitive theory and reflection theory, understand the essence of the category's "matter" and "consciousness", the nature of the interaction of living and inanimate nature, the essence of reflexology, especially collective reflexology.

Within the framework of the socioinformatiological approach in the activities of the press service, it is important to achieve the effect of information and mental identity (identity) and their unity (compliance of the policy of regional authorities

with the demands of the "collective unconscious"), as well as the unity of economic, political and information identity.

Achieving information identity between the official information policy of the government and the unofficial information policy of the people (people's policy based on existential information, on the exchange of information in the process of interpersonal communication: here and rumors, and conjectures, and guesses, and inventions, but also mature, wise judgments) should achieve a high degree of information identity (compliance, identities). Otherwise, socio-psychological mechanisms will develop: doubt, distrust, discontent, alienation in the relations between the government and the people. The most important regulator in the process of achieving information identity is the mass media and the means of political communication.

The press service should provide full information support of the reforms from the development stage to their implementation in practice. In modern conditions, people do not always have a sufficient understanding of the meaning, essence, purpose of reforms and transformations, about their mechanism, about what they will ultimately give for the common man. To eliminate this discrepancy, the task of the press service is to conduct an open and public dialogue (discussion with the public, public examination), that is, to ensure the development of a dialogical, discursive paradigm of information policy. The effect of dialogue, discourse in the system of "power — mass media — people" should be achieved on the basis of social partnership relations. Such a system of information work is designed to explain to citizens the essence of reforms, programs and projects, as well as to provide a feedback mechanism so that suggestions and comments "from the field" can be taken into account when adjusting the decisions of the authorities. This is the core function of the press service, which can be considered within the motivational paradigm or motivation of social behavior. In this case, the press service staff should study the final stage of the information process - the motivation of social behavior on the basis of information assimilated, processed by people through socio—

political and media communication in the system "power — information policy — people".

Due to the fact that culture also enters the mental world of a person, when studying the activities of the press service, it is legitimate to use a cultural paradigm. Here we are talking about the formation of information culture, the organization of media education and media education. In the "Concept of State Information Policy", special attention is paid to the mass media. It says that "the media is an effective channel for informing society about the activities of the authorities and society, about the life of society and its reaction to the actions of the authorities. These features make the media an important social institution and a necessary object of state information policy. Modern mass media not only promptly reflect world events, but are largely engaged in the analysis of information, its preliminary filtering and purposeful selection. Thanks to this, the media are a powerful means of influencing people's consciousness." Employees of the press service should "cultivate the mass media" and try to form a spiritual mass culture. This is the cultural and educational function of the press service. Thus, the press service assumes the function of socialization of citizens. In contrast to journalistic practice, the implementation of the cultural and educational function in our case acquires a more rigid pragmatic orientation - to form people's idea of the activities of the authorities, to teach them to use democratic mechanisms of influence on the authorities.

Literatures:

1. Vorobyev V.V. Information management and its evaluation criteria. M., 2006, Information management. M., 2005.
2. Information Policy: Textbook / Under the general editorship of V.D.Popov. M., 2003. pp. 436-437; Gott V.S., Semenyuk E.P., Ursul A.D. The social role of informatics. M., 1987; Semenyuk E.P. Information approach to the cognition of reality. Kiev, 1988.
3. The concept of state information policy / Under the general editorship of Finko O. A. M.,1999.